

First and final characterisation of ofmsw, horeca and sewage sludges with current systems of collection, transport, sorting and pre-treatment

Deliverable 3.3

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Lead Partner: FCC

Contributor(s): FCC, AQUALIA, UNIMORE, LAZIO, CLUBE, IRIS, MADRID

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

SCALIBUR aims at closing the gap between technological feasibility and industrial applications in the field of urban biowaste valorisation by enhancing strategic cooperation between sectors. SCALIBUR contributes to two European challenges: to reduce landfilling and the creation of a bio-based Economy in 2030 handling the recovery of urban biowaste from citizens through several municipalities, the production chain of bio-based products by innovative technologies, and equally important, direct collaboration with the future end-users.

Within WP3 all the biowaste fractions will be physically characterised for the optimisation of the compositions to be fed in work packages 4 to 6.

Within "D3.3 First and final characterisation of OFMSW, HORECA and sewage sludges with current systems of collection, transport, sorting and pre-treatment" characterisation protocols are followed in order to obtain the characterisations made at collection points consisting in a calculation of the biodegradable content and the type of contaminants and inert materials contained. This will serve as the basis to compare the improvement levels reached by the implementation of best practices in the municipalities participating in the pilots regarding OFMSW and HORECA waste. Sewage sludge is also characterized in order to analyse its bioelectrochemical conversion into bioplastics and biopesticides.

"D3.3 First and final characterisation of OFMSW, HORECA and sewage sludges with current systems of collection, transport, sorting and pre-treatment" has two delivery dates. The present document shows the information regarding the first delivery date in Month 6 (April 2019). This document will be actualised in the second delivery date in Month 42 (April 2022).

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